

Formulation and Evaluation of Biodegradable Films of Levofloxacin for the Management of Periodontitis

Mr. Rishikesh Vijay Patil*, Dr. Revathi A Gupta, Mrs. Shivangni Rathore, Mr. Anubhav Shrivastava, Mr. Vinay Mahajan, Mr. Rahul Maskawde

Institute of Pharmacy, Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam University, Indore

Abstract The present study succeeded in the formulation and evaluation of biodegradable films of levofloxacin for the management of periodontitis. Processing factors such as chitosan and plasticizer concentration have significantly affected the physical characteristics of film and were found within acceptable range. Chitosan concentration has negatively affected drug release and positively affected T90 due to altered matrix density. On the contrary, plasticizer concentration has positively affected the rate of drug release and negatively affected T90 of drug attributed to increased membrane permeability. This study succeeded in the fabrication of levofloxacin biodegradable, mucoadhesive chitosan film which is cheap, less resource-requiring film devices having greater market potential to administer medicament locally into the periodontal pockets for the management of periodontitis.

Keywords Formulation, Evaluation, Biodegradable Films, Levofloxacin, Periodontitis

1. Introduction

Periodontitis is a globally widespread bacterial infectious disease which is characterized by the damage of the periodontal tissues followed by the loss in periodontal ligament and alveolar bone.(1) Periodontal disease is considered as the major cause of tooth loss and other oral problems, and it is also associated with other diseases such as diabetes mellitus, atherosclerotic vascular disease, infective endocarditis, and chronic nephritis.(2)

Levofloxacin, is an antibiotic used to treat a number of bacterial infections like acute bacterial sinusitis, pneumonia, H. pylori (in combination with other medications), urinary tract infections, chronic prostatitis, and some types of gastroenteritis. Along with other antibiotics it may be used to treat tuberculosis, meningitis, or pelvic inflammatory disease.

2. Materials and Methods

Table 1: Formulation Levofloxacin Biodegradable Chitosan Films

Formulation	Chitosan (g)	Propylene glycol (g)	Glutaraldehyde (g)	Levofloxacin (g)
F-1	0.6	0.12	0.02	0.1
F-2	0.6	0.16	0.02	0.1
F-3	0.6	0.20	0.02	0.1
F-4	0.6	0.24	0.02	0.1
F-5	0.7	0.12	0.02	0.1
F-6	0.7	0.16	0.02	0.1
F-7	0.7	0.20	0.02	0.1

F-8	0.7	0.24	0.02	0.1
F-9	0.8	0.12	0.02	0.1
F-10	0.8	0.16	0.02	0.1
F-11	0.8	0.20	0.02	0.1
F-12	0.8	0.24	0.02	0.1

Calibration Curve for Levofloxacin

Preparation of standard solutions

Preparation of standard solutions

The levofloxacin reference standard solution (200.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was prepared by accurately weighing 20.0 mg of levofloxacin reference in a 100.0 mL volumetric flask. The volume was completed with methanol. This flask was sonicated for 25 min. The above solution was diluted in a 100 mL volumetric flask with methanol to obtain a final solution containing 10.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of levofloxacin. ⁽¹²³⁾

Determination of maximum absorption λ_{max}

From the standard solution (200.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) approximately 3.0 mL was taken and scanned from 200 to 400 nm with HP 8453 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The methanol was used as blank. Levofloxacin presented maximum absorption at 298 nm. ⁽¹²³⁾

Calibration curve of Levofloxacin

The calibration curve was constructed by analyzing 6 different concentrations of standard solution, prepared on the same day. The range of solutions varied from 3.0 to 8.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. ⁽¹²³⁾

Table 2: Formulation Levofloxacin Biodegradable Chitosan Films

Formulation	Chitosan (g)	Propylene glycol (g)	Glutaraldehyde (g)	Levofloxacin (g)
F-1	0.6	0.12	0.02	0.1
F-2	0.6	0.16	0.02	0.1
F-3	0.6	0.20	0.02	0.1
F-4	0.6	0.24	0.02	0.1
F-5	0.7	0.12	0.02	0.1
F-6	0.7	0.16	0.02	0.1
F-7	0.7	0.20	0.02	0.1
F-8	0.7	0.24	0.02	0.1
F-9	0.8	0.12	0.02	0.1
F-10	0.8	0.16	0.02	0.1
F-11	0.8	0.20	0.02	0.1
F-12	0.8	0.24	0.02	0.1

Fabrication of levofloxacin biodegradable chitosan films

Periodontal films were prepared by solvent casting method ⁽¹²⁴⁾. The films were prepared as per formula given in Table 2.

Accurately weighed quantity of Chitosan was dissolved in 40 ml of 0.5% acetic acid solution and stirred for 24 h for complete solubilization. The weighed amount of Levofloxacin was incorporated in the polymer solution and stirred for 6 h.

A measured quantity of propylene glycol (as a plasticizer) was added. After deaerating under vacuum for 6 h, the solution was poured on levelled glass mould having size of $5 \times 4 \times 1.2$ cm and placed in an oven maintained at 50°C (Tempo Industrial Corporation, Mumbai). The system was left undisturbed for 24 h to allow complete evaporation.

The formed films were completely removed from the glass mould and punched out in desired size, wrapped in aluminium foil and stored in desiccators until further use.

For crosslinking, the films were dipped into the solution of crosslinking agent glutaraldehyde for 24 h and then removed and dried. Placebo films without drug containing only CS and plasticizer were prepared as control.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 3: Characterization of Levofloxacin

S. No	Test	Specification	Results
1	Description	White or yellow light crystalline powder	A white crystalline powder
2	Loss on drying	≤3 W/W	2.17% W/W
3	Solubility	Freely soluble in glacial acetic acid, chloroform; sparingly soluble in water	Complies
4	Melting point	225 °C - 227 °C	224 °C - 226 °C

Table 4: IR Spectral Interpretation of Levofloxacin

S.No	Functional group	Observed peak
1	>C=O of lactum ring	1723 cm ⁻¹
2	>C=O of quinolone moiety	1884 cm ⁻¹
3	Aromatic C-H stretching	2935 cm ⁻¹
4	O-H group of carboxyl moiety	3275.5 cm ⁻¹

Figure 1: FTIR of Levofloxacin

Figure 2: FTIR of Chitosan

Figure 3: Standard Curve of Levofloxacin

The calibration curve showed linearity over a concentration range from 3.0 to 8.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Evaluation of Levofloxacin Biodegradable Films

Thickness and Weight Variation

The thickness and weight variation of films are directly associated with the uniformity and accuracy of dosing. The average thickness of all prepared periodontal films F-1 to F-12 ranged from 0.29 ± 0.05 mm to 0.35 ± 0.06 mm (Table 5). Weight variation values varied between 5.96 ± 0.07 mg and 6.31 ± 0.08 mg ($n = 3$).

Table 5: Thickness and Weight Variation Levofloxacin Biodegradable Chitosan Films

Formulation	Thickness ^a (mm \pm SD)	Weight variation ^a (mg \pm SD)
F-1	0.29 ± 0.05	6.26 ± 0.05
F-2	0.32 ± 0.08	6.14 ± 0.06
F-3	0.35 ± 0.06	6.31 ± 0.08
F-4	0.32 ± 0.06	5.96 ± 0.07
F-5	0.30 ± 0.07	6.40 ± 0.08
F-6	0.32 ± 0.08	6.20 ± 0.06
F-7	0.32 ± 0.05	6.28 ± 0.02
F-8	0.31 ± 0.05	6.26 ± 0.04
F-9	0.32 ± 0.03	6.20 ± 0.01
F-10	0.33 ± 0.04	6.27 ± 0.02
F-11	0.34 ± 0.02	6.13 ± 0.04
F-12	0.32 ± 0.02	6.23 ± 0.06

SD (standard deviation)

^a Result is presented as mean \pm SD, $n = 3$

Table 6: Uniformity of Drug Content of Levofloxacin Biodegradable Chitosan Films

Formulation	Total drug content ^a (%)
F-1	95.70 ± 2.67
F-2	96.24 ± 2.27
F-3	95.16 ± 2.43
F-4	94.19 ± 2.96
F-5	94.50 ± 2.12
F-6	95.20 ± 3.07
F-7	93.70 ± 2.32
F-8	94.00 ± 2.14
F-9	97.40 ± 2.46
F-10	96.50 ± 2.49
F-11	98.72 ± 2.19
F-12	95.80 ± 2.27

SD (standard deviation)

^a Result is presented as mean ± SD, n = 3

Figure 4: Swelling Index of Levofloxacin Biodegradable Chitosan Films

Figure 5: Scanning electron microscopic images showing surface morphology of a–c placebo films and d–f drug-loaded films at different resolutions

Figure 6: In Vitro Drug Release Studies In vitro Drug Release of Levofloxacin Biodegradable Chitosan Films

Table 7: Kinetic Modelling for Optimized Batch F-11

Batch code	r ² value			Korsmeyer-Peppas model	
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi model	r ² value	n value
F-11	0.70	0.83	0.88	0.97	0.624

In Vitro Antibacterial Activity of Periodontal Films

The antibacterial activity of the films was estimated by measuring zone of inhibition against *S. aureus* (ATCC25323) and *E. coli* (ATCC25922). Zone of inhibition was calculated for optimized polymeric film (batch F-11) containing Levofloxacin, placebo film at every day until 5 days (Fig.17).

Levofloxacin films exhibited good zone of inhibition against *S. aureus* with value of 40.1 ± 0.52 mm whereas lesser activity for *E. coli* having zone of inhibition of 36.53 ± 1.55 mm on the first day of the assay and then it slowly decreased to 8.5 ± 0.40 mm and 7.24 ± 0.48 mm after 5 days of incubation (Fig. 17).

Figure 7: Anti-Bacterial Activity of Levofloxacin Film

4. Conclusion

The present study succeeded in the fabrication of biodegradable, mucoadhesive film of chitosan by solvent casting. Processing factors such as chitosan and plasticizer concentration have significantly affected the physical characteristics of film and were found within acceptable range.

Chitosan concentration has negatively affected drug release and positively affected T_{90} due to altered matrix density. On the contrary, plasticizer concentration has positively affected the rate of drug release and negatively affected T_{90} of drug attributed to increased membrane permeability.

This study succeeded in the fabrication of levofloxacin biodegradable, mucoadhesive chitosan film which is cheap, less resource-requiring film devices having greater market potential to administer medicament locally into the periodontal pockets for the management of periodontitis.

References

- [1]. Preshaw P, Alba A, Herrera D, et al. Periodontitis and diabetes: a two-way relationship. *Diabetologia*. 2012;55(1):21–31. doi:10.1007/s00125-011-2342-y2.
- [2]. Chen X, Wu G, Feng Z, et al. Advanced biomaterials and their potential applications in the treatment of periodontal disease. *Crit Rev Biotechnol*. 2016;36(4):760–775. doi:10.3109/07388551.2015.10356933.
- [3]. Baranov N, Popa M, Atanase LI, Ichim DL. Polysaccharide-based drug delivery systems for the treatment of periodontitis. *Molecules*. 2021;26(9):2735. doi:10.3390/molecules260927354.

- [4]. Tominari T, Sanada A, Ichimaru R, et al. Gram-positive bacteria cell wall-derived lipoteichoic acid induces inflammatory alveolar bone loss through prostaglandin E production in osteoblasts. *Sci Rep.* 2021;11(1):1–12. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-92744-55.
- [5]. Herrera D, Matesanz P, Bascones-Martínez A, Sanz M. Local and systemic antimicrobial therapy in periodontics. *J Evid Based Dent Pract.* 2012;12(3):50–60. doi:10.1016/S1532-3382(12)70013-16.
- [6]. Ahmed MG, Harish N, Charyulu RN, Prabhu P. Formulation of chitosan-based ciprofloxacin and diclofenac film for periodontitis therapy. *Trop J Pharm Res.* 2009;8(1):33–41. doi:10.4314/tjpr.v8i1.147107.
- [7]. Greenstein G, Polson A. The role of local drug delivery in the management of periodontal diseases: a comprehensive review. *J Periodontol.* 1998;69(5):507–520. doi:10.1902/jop.1998.69.5.5078.
- [8]. Khan G, Yadav SK, Patel RR, Nath G, Bansal M, Mishra B. Development and evaluation of biodegradable chitosan films of metronidazole and levofloxacin for the management of periodontitis. *AapsPharmscitech.* 2016;17(6):1312–1325. doi:10.12 08/s12249-015-0466-y
- [9]. Maniruzzaman M, Boateng JS, Snowden MJ, et al. A review of hot-melt extrusion: process technology to pharmaceutical products. *ISRN Pharm* 2012;2012:1–9.
- [10]. Patel VF, Liu F, Brown MB. Advances in oral transmucosal drug delivery. *J Control Release* 2011;153:106–116.
- [11]. Borges AF, Silva C, Coelho JF, et al. Oral films: current status and future perspectives: I - Galenical development and quality attributes. *J Control Release* 2015;206:1–19.
- [12]. Sharma D, Kaur D, Verma S, et al. Fast dissolving oral films technology: a recent trend for an innovative oral drug delivery system. *Int J Drug Deliv* 2015;7:60–75.
- [13]. Kang-Mieler JJ, Osswald CR, Mieler WF. Advances in ocular drug delivery: emphasis on the posterior segment. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv* 2014;11:1–14.
- [14]. Castro PM, Fonte P, Sousa F, et al. Oral films as breakthrough tools for oral delivery of proteins/peptides. *J Control Release* 2015;211:63–73.
- [15]. Barbu E, Verestiuc L, Nevell TG, et al. Polymeric materials for ophthalmic drug delivery: trends and perspectives. *J Mater Chem* 2006;16:3439–3443.
- [16]. Achouri D, Alhanout K, Piccerelle P, et al. Recent advances in ocular drug delivery. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm* 2013;39:1599–1617.
- [17]. Hearnden V, Sankar V, Hull K, et al. New developments and opportunities in oral mucosal drug delivery for local and systemic disease. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* 2012;64:16–28.
- [18]. Janßen EM, Schliephacke R, Breitenbach A, et al. Drug printing by flexographic printing technology – a new manufacturing process for orodispersible films. *Int J Pharm* 2013;441:818–825.
- [19]. Morales JO, McConville JT. Manufacture and characterization of mucoadhesive buccal films. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 2011;77:187–199.
- [20]. Nair AB, Kumria R, Harsha S, et al. In vitro techniques to evaluate buccal films. *J Control Release* 2013;166:10–21.
- [21]. Ng YC, Yang Z, McAuley WJ, et al. Stabilisation of amorphous drugs under high humidity using pharmaceutical thin films. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 2013;84:555–565.
- [22]. Kumari A, Sharma P, Garg V, et al. Ocular inserts – advancement in therapy of eye diseases. *J Adv Pharm Technol Res* 2010;1:291–296.
- [23]. Irfan M, Rabel S, Bukhtar Q, et al. Orally disintegrating films: a modern expansion in drug delivery system. *Saudi Pharm J* 2015;2015:1–10.
- [24]. Patel A, Cholkar K, Agrahari V, et al. Ocular drug delivery systems: an overview. *World J Pharmacol* 2015;2:47–64.
- [25]. Dixit RP, Puthli SP. Oral strip technology: overview and future potential. *J Control Release* 2009;139:94–107.
- [26]. Hao J, Heng PWS. Buccal delivery systems. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm* [Internet] 2003;29:821–832.

- [27]. Rathore KS, Nema RK, Sisodia SS. Timolol maleate a gold standard drug in glaucoma used as ocular films and inserts: an overview. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res* 2010;3:23–29.
- [28]. Juluru N. Fast dissolving oral films: a novel drug delivery system. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res* 2013;2:108–112.
- [29]. Siddiqui MDN, Garg G, Sharma PK. A short review on “a novel approach in oral fast dissolving drug delivery system and their patents”. *Adv Biol Res* 2011;5:291–303.
- [30]. Amin PM, Gangurde AB, Alai PV. Oral film technology: challenges and future scope for pharmaceutical industry. *Int J Pharm Pharm Res* 2015;3:183–203.
- [31]. Vibhooti P, Preeti K. Wafers technology—a newer approach to smart drug delivery system. *Indian J Res Pharm Biotechnol* 2013;1:428–439.
- [32]. Hoffmann EM, Breitenbach A, Breitreutz J. Advances in orodispersible films for drug delivery. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv* 2011;8:299–316.
- [33]. Prabhu SC, Parsekar SD, Shetty A, et al. Review article a review on fast dissolving sublingual films for systemic drug delivery. *Int J Pharm Chem Sci* 2014;3:501–511.
- [34]. Russo E, Selmin F, Baldassari S, et al. A focus on mucoadhesive polymers and their application in buccal dosage forms. *J Drug Deliv Sci Technol* 2015;32:113–125.
- [35]. Wening K, Breitreutz J. Oral drug delivery in personalized medicine: unmet needs and novel approaches. *Int J Pharm* 2011;404:1–9.
- [36]. Sultana Y, Jain R, Aqil M, et al. Review of ocular drug delivery. *Curr Drug Deliv* 2006;3:207–217.
- [37]. Guo R, Du X, Zhang R, et al. Bioadhesive film formed from a novel organic-inorganic hybrid gel for transdermal drug delivery system. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 2011;79:574–583.
- [38]. Boddupalli B, Mohammed Z, Nath R, et al. Mucoadhesive drug delivery system: an overview. *J Adv Pharm Technol Res* 2010;1:381–387.
- [39]. Rawas-Qalaji M, Williams CA. Advances in ocular drug delivery. *Curr Eye Res* 2012;37:345–356.
- [40]. Jadhav YG, Galgatte UC, Chaudhari PD. Challenges in formulation development of fast dissolving oral films. *Indo Am J Pharm Res* 2013;3:1746–1751.
- [41]. Perumal VA, Govender T, Lutchman D, et al. Investigating a new approach to film casting for enhanced drug content uniformity in polymeric films. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm* 2008;34:1036–1047.
- [42]. Renukuntla J, Vadlapudi AD, Patel A, et al. Approaches for enhancing oral bioavailability of peptides and proteins. *Int J Pharm* 2013;447:75–93.
- [43]. Khairnar GA, Sayyad FJ. Development of buccal drug delivery system based on mucoadhesive polymers. *Int J PharmTech Res* 2010;2:719–735.
- [44]. Chaudhary H, Gauri S, Rathee P, et al. Development and optimization of fast dissolving oro-dispersible films of granisetron HCl using Box–Behnken statistical design. *Bull Fac Pharm Cairo Univ* 2013;51:193–201.
- [45]. Landová H, Vetchý V, Gajdziok J. Evaluation of the influence of formulation and process variables on mechanical properties of oral mucoadhesive films using multivariate data analysis. *Biomed Res Int* 2014;2014:1–9.
- [46]. Juliano C, Cossu M, Pigozzi P, et al. In vitro characterization and preliminary in vivo evaluation of buccal polymeric films containing chlorhexidine. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 2008;9:1153–1158.
- [47]. Kunte S, Tandale P. Fast dissolving strips: a novel approach for the delivery of verapamil. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci* 2010;2:325–328.
- [48]. El-Setouhy DA, Shakwy N, El-Malak ABD. Formulation of a novel tianeptine sodium orodispersible film. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 2010;11:1018–1025.
- [49]. Low AQJ, Parmentier J, Khong YM, et al. Effect of type and ratio of solubilising polymer on characteristics of hot-melt extruded orodispersible films. *Int J Pharm* 2013;455:138–147.
- [50]. Preis M, Woertz C, Kleinebudde P, et al. Oromucosal film preparations: classification and characterization methods. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv* 2013;10:1–15.

- [51]. Verma S, Kumar N, Sharma PK. Buccal film: an advance technology for oral drug delivery. *Adv Biol Res* 2014;8:260–267.
- [52]. Repka MA, Gutta K, Prodduturi S, et al. Characterization of cellulosic hot-melt extruded films containing lidocaine. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 2005;59:189–196.
- [53]. Crowley MM, Zhang F. Pharmaceutical applications of hotmelt extrusion: part I. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm* 2007;33:909–926.
- [54]. Chokshi R, Zia H. Hot-melt extrusion technique: a review. *Iran J Pharm Res* 2004;3:3–16.
- [55]. Jani R, Patel D. Hot melt extrusion: an industrially feasible approach for casting orodispersible film. *Asian J Pharm Sci* 2014;10:292–305.
- [56]. Preis M, Breitzkreutz J, Sandler N. Perspective: concepts of printing technologies for oral film formulations. *Int J Pharm* 2015;494:578–584.
- [57]. Daly R, Harrington TS, Martin GD, et al. Inkjet printing for pharmaceuticals – a review of research and manufacturing. *Int J Pharm* 2015;494:554–567.
- [58]. Ali J, Arora S, Ahuja A, et al. Formulation and development of floating capsules of celecoxib: in vitro and in vivo evaluation. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 2007;8:E1–E8.
- [59]. Prabhushankar GL, Gopalkrishna B, Manjunatha KM, et al. Formulation and evaluation of levofloxacin dental films for periodontitis. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2010;2:162–168.
- [60]. Cao N, Yang X, Fu Y. Effects of various plasticizers on mechanical and water vapor barrier properties of gelatin films. *Food Hydrocoll* 2009;23:729–735.
- [61]. Preis M, Pein M, Breitzkreutz J. Development of a tastemaskedorodispersible film containing dimenhydrinate. *Pharmaceutics* 2012;4:551–562.
- [62]. Preis M, Knop K, Breitzkreutz J. Mechanical strength test for orodispersible and buccal films. *Int J Pharm* 2014;461:22–29.
- [63]. Heng PWS, Chan LW, Ong KT. Influence of storage conditions and type of plasticizers on ethylcellulose and acrylate films from aqueous dispersions. *J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2003;6:334–344.
- [64]. Liew KB, Tan YTF, Peh KK. Effect of polymer, plasticizer and filler on orally disintegrating film. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm* 2014;40:110–119.
- [65]. Dong Z, Wang Q, Du Y. Alginate/gelatin blend films and their properties for drug controlled release. *J Memb Sci* 2006;280:37–44.

